

Reintegration Roadblocks: Challenges Facing Effective Management of Returnees by NCFRMI Steps for action.

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Abstract

The provision of advice, tailored to the individual, starts before the returnee leaves Germany and focuses on labour market prospects, training and knowledge transfer. Information is also provided about suitable vacancies with local employers in the country of origin. Upon their arrival in the country of origin, CIM is available to support the returnees' reintegration into the workplace and to facilitate networking. In addition, some refugees are selected to receive advice and training so that they can set up their own businesses. Reintegration assistance includes, for example, arrivals service, advice and support with official, medical and charitable institutions, job qualification programmes, help with looking for a job, support in setting up a business. The support will be offered in-kind. Reintegration assistance is available to voluntary returnees and those who have been obliged to return to a selection of third countries. Nigeria and Guinea feature among these as the only countries among the all West Africa region. The present paper is on the challenges constraining effective management of returnees by the NCFRMI.

Introduction

Many refugees and labour migrants wish to return their home countries, sometimes after spending years or even decades abroad. However, they often find it difficult to reintegrate into a society that has changed dramatically while they were away. GIZ therefore supports the social reintegration of returnees in their home countries. Since early 2015, GIZ has been supporting former civil war refugees returning to Somalia, for example. Many have spent years away from their home country and are now coming back to communities which are ill-equipped to deal with their return. In order to avoid tensions between returnees and local communities, GIZ – on behalf of the German Federal Ministry for Economic Cooperation and Development (BMZ) – is working to create new prospects for local people. In Kismayo, the third largest city in Somalia, unemployment is extremely high, especially among young people. Young returnees, internally displaced persons and local people are therefore being trained together in urgently needed occupations. The training offers reliable prospects for the future, strengthens social cohesion and helps the Somali authorities to ensure that enough skilled workers are available locally. Women's empowerment is a target area of investment: women learn a trade or management skills, enabling them to set up their own businesses. Migrants who have studied and worked in Germany often bring much-needed expertise with them on their return. They pass on this knowledge to their employers and colleagues and thus contribute to their home countries' development. Returnees are bridge-builders, linking their personal and professional

networks in Germany and their countries of origin. On behalf of the German Federal Ministry for Economic Cooperation and Development (BMZ), the Centre for International Migration and Development (CIM), which is jointly run by GIZ and the International Placement Services (ZAV) of the German Federal Employment Agency, has been advising and supporting returning experts since 1980. During this period, it has provided advice and financial support for more than 12,000 skilled workers in order to facilitate their return and reintegration into the workplace in their countries of origin.

Internally Displaced Persons

The phenomenon of internal displacement has been on the increase in recent years, and the trend continues to rise. The former Secretary-General of the United Nations, Ban Ki-Moon stated in 2014 that displacement remains arguably the most significant humanitarian challenge facing the world. For instance, there were over 30 million Internally Displaced Persons (IDPs) in the world as of 2014, with about one-half of this figure in Sub-Saharan Africa alone, with Nigeria taking the lead (Ban Ki-Moon, 2014). As the number of IDPs continues to increase, attempts at management become more challenging for these countries. Notably, global efforts at managing displacement have concentrated more on refugees than IDPs, yet the latter equally constitute a challenge to global civilization. Internal displacement in Nigeria is a recurring decimal and large-scale phenomenon engulfing virtually every part of the country. The country has been through many waves of displacement, both small and large scale. Post-independence Nigeria had its share of IDPs. During Nigeria's civil war between 1967 and 1970, a good number of eastern Nigerians crossed Nigeria's border to become refugees in Cameroon, Chad, Niger, but the majority of south easterners were internally displaced within Nigeria. Forced migration and internal displacement in and into Nigeria in the last 63 years of independence has been triggered by violent conflict, natural disasters and environmental degradation, generalized violence, inter-communal and inter-ethnic clashes, disputes over land, boundary conflicts between indigenous people and settlers, communal and ethno-religious clashes, electoral violence as well as other forms of human rights violations.

National Commission for Refugees, Migrants and Internally Displaced Persons (NCFRMI) and Returnees to Nigeria

The NCFRMI was set up in 1989 with the main responsibility of providing an overall framework and policy for protecting and managing refugees, asylum-seekers and internally displaced persons. It was also given the mandate to counsel the government on policy issues regarding returnees, refugees in Nigeria (Biodun, 2016). The establishment of the commission was backed by Decree Number 52, currently known as the chapter N21 Laws of the Federation of Nigeria, 2004 (Done, 2017). The enactment of the NCFR act was informed by international and regional conventions on refugees and asylum seekers, namely the 1951 UN refugee convention and its 1967 protocol, as well as the organization of African unity convention (Jacklyn, 2016). Since 2002 the commission has been saddled with the responsibility of assisting resettling, rehabilitating and reintegrating persons who are returnees from countries

abroad, internally displaced due to environmental disasters and conflicts. To achieve this, the commission collaborates with other stakeholders to achieve maximum functionality (Bernard, 2017). According to NCFRMI (2018), the exact number of Nigerian immigrants cannot be accurately determined, therefore, estimates based on data got from the world health organization (WHO), International organization for migrants (IOM), European Union (EU), United Nations Development Programme (UNDP). The country's emigrant's population ranges between 836,832 and 3,041,284, constituting 0.6 percent of the total population of Nigeria.

The major destination countries for these emigrants are the United States (452,172) the united kingdom and northern Ireland (384,314), Cameroon (215,621), Italy (148,073), Spain (136,885), Germany (222,687), Cote d'Ivoire (93,761), Libya (106,834), Benin (92,575), Ghana (82,380), and Sudan (75,275). The volumes of migrants moving out of the country have been increasing between 2010 and 2018, the estimated proportion of Nigerian emigrants in the US increased by 3.6 percent while that of Cameroon increased by 0.9 percent. Similarly, the male representation for the US in both 2010 and 2018 was higher with 56 and 57 percent, respectively. On the other hand, Italy, Ireland, Canada and Burkina Faso host more Nigerian female immigrants than male (Johns, 2019). He also expressed the availability of UNHCR to work with the state in the facilitation of tripartite framework for the return and reintegration process. Dietrich (2015) reaffirmed that "given IDPs increased vulnerability including the September 11, 2015 attack on an IDPs camp in Adamawa State, IDPs have called on the government to increase security measures in order to ensure the protection of IDPs and humanitarian actors in camps. While most of the individuals are fleeing violence, many reported that they are also fleeing a humanitarian crisis defined by food insecurity, loss of livelihoods, insufficient services, and adequate protection. considering the level of insecurity in IDP camps, it has been observed that many IDPs had a heightened sense of personal security, and described their self protection strategies in the camps like this: "we protect ourselves by creating well-fortified and secured camps to safeguard lives and property, conducting aggressive intelligence gathering on activities like free medical treatment and, condemning erring personnel of rape and sexual offences accordingly (Dietrich, 2015). There are a number of challenges that have negatively affected returnee's management in Nigeria. These challenges are complex and overlapping.

Reintegration

There are conceptual problems regarding reintegration, sometimes used inter-changeably with integration, of return migrants. The Oxford Dictionary Arowolo defines integration as the intermixing of persons previously segregated; and reintegration as the process of integrating back into society. When applied to return migrants, the two words do not relate to the same process.

Preston (1993a: 2-4) has argued that within migratory cycles, the process of integration is one of adaptation; a process of give and take on either side as people learn to live together. At destinations, this adaptation takes place between the host community and their guests, while at

places of origin it is between those who have returned and those who remained at home during their absence. The extent of integration, she argues, will depend upon a series of constantly changing contextual factors, ranging from contingencies of the physical environment, climate and pestilence, as well as social and economic circumstances. The point is that integration is applied to the return migrant as if there was no integration experience at the point of origin prior to migration. Preston's argument that the term reintegration may be taken to imply that the social and economic environment to which people return has not changed since they left is unrealistic. There is nothing about the process of reintegration to suggest that such a process is only feasible under conditions of graveyard social and economic stability and quiet. Integration or reintegration can take place in the face of changes in the economy, society and the environment.

If it can be assumed that a potential migrant is a fully integrated member of his place of origin, the decision to migrate and his actual departure from the home environment should not rob him of the status as a formerly integrated member of his home base. Upon return from a chosen place of destination, he needs to be reintegrated into the original society to which he was already acculturated. This process applies to returnees from voluntary migration and to those returning from various forms of forced movements, including persons moving out of their countries and in exile, or living in "in exile" as a result of internal displacement.

Reintegration Strategies

Within the context of studies on voluntary migration, return migration has long remained invisible. This is largely because return migration tends to be a private, individual or family affair. However, over the past three decades, the increased scale of international return migration has made it conspicuous, and the growing problems of reintegration have in many cases led governments and agencies to intervene (Preston, 1993b: 2-5). Intervention strategies include pre-return or on-arrival orientation to prepare for changes and difficulties to be encountered; provision of financial and investment advice for those hoping to start business or acquire property (Athukorala, 1986); provision of information about qualification and skill recognition for labour market entry; language training for children born abroad and their preparation for entering the school system at "home" (Dumon, 1976). Despite such support strategies, many return migrants still face acute problems of reintegration, ranging from joblessness and social maladjustment to boredom and frustration. In cases of accompanying foreign dependants, they tend to encounter, on the one hand, the problem of adaptation between themselves and their relations and, on the other hand, between themselves and the community. In such situations, both foreign wives and children are reported to have experienced loss of identity and trauma (Gmelch, 1980). Both the host country and country of origin often jointly plan the return of refugees to their home country, invariably with the assistance of international agencies. However, reintegration of returning refugees is even more challenging because their return, although often planned and orchestrated, tends to be dramatic and chaotic. Unlike voluntary migration, construction of frameworks for analysing the integration of refugees into their country of origin is recent and poorly developed. Part of the problem is that while the

numbers involved tend to be large, those who return independently are far in excess of those who take part in organized schemes (Rogge, 1991). Some governments have utilized policy and legal instruments as a strategy for achieving the integration of returning migrants, particularly refugees. For example, Zimbabwe enacted several Acts of Parliament in support of the country's scheme to reintegrate an estimated 300,000 persons who had left the country to seek refuge abroad during the prolonged war of independence which ended in 1980. But implementation of these Acts met with many different problems, including resistance from the civil service establishment, poor information and inadequate commitment of the Government to ensure compliance by the public (Makanya, 1992).

Challenges Constraining Effective Management of Returnees By The NCFRMI *Funding*

In a recent survey research carried out, respondents disclosed that although IDPs management agencies in Nigeria get funds mainly through revenue, international aids and donations. The funds they get are more often than not insufficient to meet the increasing needs of IDPs in the country (Osagioduwa & Oluwakorede, 2016). Consequently, insufficiency of funds results in deficiency in manpower, commodities, infrastructure, equipment and mobility. Where there is paucity of funds, standard facilities will be unavailable and agencies will be inefficient. The under supply of funds is attributed to low budgeting for emergencies. This therefore justifies the position of olagunju cited in osagioduwa and oluwakorede (2016) that government in Nigeria does not have an adequate machinery in place to address IDPs issues and the organizations created by the government possess minimal capacity to handle IDPs related problems.

Corruption

Corrupt office holders in government, and in IDPs management agencies alike, have been accused on several occasions diverting funds and relief materials meant for IDPs for their personal use and for their relatives or friends. A situation that reduces the efficiency of the agencies concerned in managing IDPs.

Overlapping IDPs Management Institutions

Improperly defined, unclear and overlapping policies and institutions have been identified as a challenge confronting IDPs management agencies. The overlapping responsibilities hinder agencies in the discharge of their duties. In terms of overlapping institutions, it was noticed from the testimony of key informants from government agencies that the government has established several IDPs management institutions or agencies with similar mandates and structures (Osagioduwa & Oluwakorede, 2016). According to them, a clear example cited by key informants is that of the responsibility of catering for refugees in the country and not IDPs.

It is arguable understandable that as a result of upsurge of IDPs in the country, its mandate has been extended to include the responsibilities of NEMA/SEMA. Today, NCFR has eventually but nominally metamorphosed into the National Commission for Refugees, Migrants and Internally Displaced persons. Considering the mandates and organizational structures of the National Commission for Refugees and NEMA one can opine that both them are analogues. Based on this, both agencies are left with the question of who has the responsibility of doing this or that, what has been done, and what has not been done already. In situations like this a significant part of the job risks being left undone, Beyond the overlapping functions of the above stated organization established by the government, the partnering NGOs and other humanitarian organizations get confused as to which of the two government establishments to work with.

Attitude of Host Communities

Sometimes as internally displaced persons over-burden existing community services, resources and job or economic livelihood opportunities, tension arises between the two populations, making effective local integration difficult (Kangiwa, 2012). Cost of living in host communities increases, especially cost of food, housing, healthcare and education. In spite of this ugly situation, it has been observed that a good number of host communities are allowed to benefit from the items. This therefore, reducing or shorting the ratio meant for the IDPs. Durosaro and Ajiboye (2011) observed that influx of nondisplaced young people who took advantage of porous IDP camps to enjoy humanitarian service and later leave for their stable homes or businesses, thus making it difficult to ordinarily identify the real target individuals. This observation is in tandem with the findings of Laden (2013) that fractions between IDPs and host communities resulting from concentration of assistance to IDPs and scarcity of resources for distribution are major hindrances to IDPs management.

Barriers to return

Obstacles that Member States face to effectively return TCNs to West African countries include:

- i. Returnees may not want to be returned or be fearful of return, as this would imply accepting that their emigration attempt has failed and possibly losing face vis-à-vis the home community as they return empty-handed;
- ii. Lack of cooperation by diplomatic representations in the EU Member States and/or competent authorities in the countries of origin regarding the issuing of travel documents for forced returns (e.g. no, or a significantly delayed, reply); These obstacles also arise in the return of TCNs to other countries

Specific problems in relation to return and reintegration to West Africa reported by Member States include:

- i. Not all West African countries have diplomatic representations in each EU Member States. As a result, interviews with returnees cannot always take place. This

- exacerbates the problem mentioned above, and may result in even lengthier procedures to obtain travel documents for (forced) returnees;
- ii. An unstable internal situation in some of the countries of Western Africa, including more recently: the health risks can impede both return and reintegration;
 - iii. Difficulty to find local/competent NGO partners in some countries / regions of return, making it difficult to provide reintegration assistance and to monitor and follow-up, especially in remote areas of West African countries;
 - iv. Lack of infrastructure to cater for the reintegration process and activities of returnees. For example in Nigeria, this relates to the saturation of the housing market, poor transport infrastructure, widespread corruption, unreliable power supply affecting economic activities, etc.
 - v. Relatively high cost of living and housing in some Western African countries. For example in Lagos (Nigeria) house rentals are often not affordable by returnees;

Summary and Conclusion

According to the National Bureau of statistics (2019), unemployment is the highest factor that pushes Nigerians out of the country in search of greener pastures. In addition, the level of insecurity and political instability in the nation has seen to many citizens leaving. From the findings of the study, others leave the country due to lack of basic amenities; there are good roads, schools, hospitals, electricity and these migrants had hopes of settling in quickly in their host countries. After the news of Libyan slave markets went around in 2017 many migrants, including Nigerians stuck in North Africa decides to return home. However, those returning to Nigeria complained that they faced the same problems they left behind. More than 7,300 Nigerians returned home from Libya in 2019 with the help of International Organisations and the Nigerian Government. Sadly, these returnees have not been fully given psycho-social support and reintegration back into the Nigerian society. Some that have kept in camps have been abandoned and left as preys for rapists and criminals, especially the women. The ultimate desire of every returnee into Nigeria is to relocate back to him or her community of origin, pick up the broken pieces of their lives and rebuild their means of livelihood. As Nigeria intensifies the battle against insecurity, unemployment and poor standard of living, agencies were created to help returnees fully incorporate into their own country they left due to insecurity, unemployment and poor living conditions. Consequently, the National Commission For Refugees, Migrants and Internally Displaced Persons was created. The body was tasked with the responsibility of assisting returnees settle in. the body was to help returnees in the provision of food and shelter psychological and social support. Sadly, the NCFRMI has not been able to totally perform its functions. The body is challenged by poor funding. This is because the government has so much to cater for, and it is taking a toll on the function of the NCFRMI. Another serious anomaly that has inhabited the function for the NCFRMI is corruption. The body usually diverts funds meant for the rehabilitation and support of the returnees and internally displaced persons. Returnees have not been properly taken care of because the

NCFRMI have not been fully operational. There are other bodies in the country like NEMA and SEMA performing the same function, and it becomes difficult for returnees, especially those in camps to know which officials are catering for them given the overlapping IDPs and returnees management agencies. In Nigeria, returnees are facing emotional and social stress. Most of the returnees are stigmatized by their fellow citizens, and this is damaging psychologically. The intention of government in helping returnees to be reintegrated into society has not worked very well due to the corrupt and insincere attitude of government and NCFRMI officials.

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